
THE INFLUENCE OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE ON THE MENTAL HEALTH OF MILLENNIAL GENERATION WORKERS IN YOGYAKARTA SPECIAL REGION

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Abstract

The research had the objective to analyze the effect of work life balance on the mental health of millennial generation employees of the Yogyakarta Special Region. This research includes causal associative research with quantitative approach. The sampling method was simple random sampling with the Slovin formula at a critical value of 10% and get results from 131 respondents. Primary data was conducted using questionnaire through google forms. The statistical tests used are validity test, reliability test, normality test, heteroscedasticity test, linearity test, simple linear regression analysis, t test and analysis of the coefficient of determination with the SPSS Statistic 26.0 Program. The results of data analysis indicated that a positive and significant influence on work life balance to mental health with a correlation value of 0.667. Effective contribution from work life balance to predict mental health by 41.8% and the remaining 58.2% influenced by other factors not examined in this study. Thus, it can be concluded that the hypothesis in this research is accepted.

Keywords: Work Life Balance, Mental Health

Introduction

Labor Law No. 13 of 2003 Chapter I Article 1 Paragraph 2 states that workers are those who are able to carry out work in order to produce services or goods to meet their own or community needs. The population of a country is broadly divided into 2 categories, namely labor and non-labor. If an individual has entered working age, they will be classified as a labor force. In Indonesia, there is a working age limit that is applied, which is between the ages of 15-64 years.

A survey conducted by [1] entitled "The Deloitte Global 2022 Gen Z and Millennial Survey" shows the views of generation Z and millennials regarding the world of work. The survey shows where 32% of generation Z and 39% of Millennials make work life balance the main thing that can make them feel at home in their workplace. In second place is the opportunity to learn then the third is a high salary.

These results show that work life balance is an important thing that will be considered by Millennials and generation Z to stay at home in their company.

According to Ramadhini (2023), the population in the productive age range, namely 15-65 years, is predicted to be greater than the unproductive age range, namely < 15 years and > 65 years in 2030. This phenomenon is deemed necessary to be utilized as well as possible, especially by the Millennial Generation, which will later replace the position of generation X. For now, the total majority of workers are generation X, and then the second largest position is workers from the Millennial Generation. The number of generation X workers is indeed greater because generation X has entered the workforce first, but in the future it will be the Millennial Generation who will soon replace their predecessors and dominate the number of workers. Thus, the Millennial Generation requires attention because of their growing number in the world of work data from BPS-Statistics Indonesia (2023) regarding the State of the Labor Force in Indonesia February 2023 (Page 31) which is shown in Table 1.1 below:

Table 1.1 Employment Status by Age Group
As of February 2023

Age Group (year)	Work
15 -19	4.668.215
20 - 24	13.195.089
25 - 29	16.000.069
30 - 34	16.405.596
35 - 39	14.493.906
40 - 44	15.987.583
45 - 49	14.997.739
50 - 54	13.362.946
55 - 59	10.646.349
60 +	16.875.019
Total	138.632.511

Source: BPS Employment 2023

In Table 1.1 above, it can be seen that the total number of workers from the age of 15 years to 60+ years is 138,632,511. The largest number is dominated by workers who fall into the Millennial Generation category, namely the age range from 20-24 years to 40-44 years with a total of 76,082,243 thousand people or 54.88%.

Based on Central BPS data on the profile of the Indonesian Millennial Generation, the provisions of the Millennial Generation category are those born between the years (1980-2000) who are now aged 23-43 years. Seen in Table 1.2, it appears that the labor force categorized as the Millennial Generation is in the age range of 20-24 years to 40-44 years with a percentage of 49.35% or 611,150 people. The labor force population according to BPS D.I.Yogyakarta in 2023 (2023:44) in February 2023 was 1,238,400 thousand people (male and female).

Table 1.2 Percentage of Labor Force by Age Group and Gender in D.I. Yogyakarta as of February 2023.

Age Group (year)	Male	Female	Number (%)
15 - 19	4.07	2.59	3.41
20 - 24	7.77	8.58	8.13
25 - 29	10.55	10.62	10.58
30 - 34	11.07	8.27	9.82
35 - 39	10.38	10.67	10.51
40 - 44	9.81	10.93	10.31
45 - 49	10.46	10.86	10.64
50 - 54	9.63	9.16	9.42
55 - 59	8.20	9.34	8.71
60 +	18.05	18.99	18.47
DIY	100.00/55.44	100.00/44.56	100.00

Source: Sakernas February 2023

Looking at current conditions, the workforce is dominated by the Millennial Generation. Millennials who dominate the world of work need to be considered in order to benefit the company, especially in terms of health both physical and mental health is a very important aspect for every phase of human life. Mental health in the workplace is how every employee who works and carries out work activities needs good mental health in order to remain productive and contribute to the company.

The influence of the desire for fulfillment of work-life balance factors on the mental health of Millennial Generation workers is interesting to analyze in more depth. This is an effort to develop employee enthusiasm for work. Thus, times have changed, where income is no longer the main consideration for employees in finding a job. There are other factors that are more taken into consideration, namely mental health. In relation to mental health, the concept of work-life balance is studied as a concept that balances personal and work life [4].

Previous studies have been conducted and proven that work-life balance has an impact on employee performance, but these studies have never been conducted in relation to employee mental health and specifically in the context of Millennial Generation workers in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. Therefore, this study was conducted to conduct empirical evidence related to the role of work-life balance on the mental health of Millennial Generation workers specifically in the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

Based on the background description above, the main problem faced in this study is "How does work life balance affect the mental health of Millennial Generation workers". While the objectives to be achieved in this study are to test and analyze the effect of work life balance variables on the mental health of Millennial Generation workers.

RESEARCH METHODS

This approach is associative research with a quantitative approach with the aim of seeing whether the Work Life Balance variable can affect Mental Health for millennial generation workers in the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

The population in this study are workers who are categorized as millennial generation in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The questionnaires were distributed for approximately 3 weeks, and the workers who filled out the questionnaires were 131 respondents, but only 124 respondents could process the data. The sampling technique used was simple random sampling

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overview of Research Objects

By Age and Location/Where Employed

The following is a description of the research respondents in terms of age distribution and respondent status. For more details, see the following picture.

Looking at the age chart, workers are predominantly aged > 26 years - ≤ 28 years, amounting to 39.5%, the second is the age range < 23 years and > 28 - ≤ 33 years has the same number, amounting to 22.6%. Meanwhile, in terms of location/place of work, workers are spread across several districts in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. Yogyakarta Regency as the dominating location/place of work, the second rank is Sleman Regency.

Based on Last Education and Length of Service

The following is a description of the research respondents seen from the distribution of the last education and length of work of the respondents. For more details, see the following picture.

In terms of education strata, workers are dominated by graduates of D4/S1, which reached 51.9%, while D1/D2/D3 graduates were at 19.8%, while high school/vocational school graduates were at 22.9%. Meanwhile, S2 / S3 graduates only accumulated at 3.2%. Meanwhile, when looking at work experience, it is dominated by workers who have worked for > 1 year - ≤ 3 years, while the lowest value is 9.9% for workers who have worked for > 5 years.

Research Instrument Test

Data analysis in this study is based on the analysis steps in the SPSS application with the following data analysis results:

Validity Test and Reliability Test

The results of the validity test using the SPSS application are as follows.

Item	R count
WLB1	0.616
WLB2	0.627
WLB3	0.576
WLB4	0.644
WLB5	0.559
WLB6	0.544
KM1	0.597
KM2	0.643
KM3	0.654
KM4	0.538
KM5	0.632
KM6	0.593

As the data shown in table 2 above, referring to Sugiyono (2019) which explains that a statement is said to be valid if $r \text{ count} < r \text{ table} = 0.05$. From the results of these calculations, it can be said that all of these statements are considered valid. The same thing is also seen from the comparison of values, $Cronbach's \text{ Alpha} > 0.60$, so it is said to be reliable. So judging from the value of *Cronbach's Alpha* by referring to these criteria, the instrument is reliable. This means that the instrument has a high confidence value to be used to measure responses from respondents [12].

Classical Assumption Test

1. Normality Test

Based on the normality test, it is known that the significance value is $0.190 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the residual value is normally distributed so that it meets the requirements for regression. The results of the normality test can be presented in table 1.

Table 2. Data Normality Test

N	124
Normality Standard	> 0.05
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.190

2. Heteroscedasticity Test

Based on the heteroscedasticity test, it is known that the significance of the suitability of *work life balance* on *ABS_RES* is $0.113 > 0.05$. This means that this study does not have heteroscedasticity problems. The results of the normality test can be presented in table 2.

Table 2. Heteroscedasticity Test

Coefficients ^a					
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	
1	(Constant)	3.939	.964		.000
	X work life balance	-.066	.041	-.143	.113

a. Dependent Variable: ABS_RES

3. Linearity Test

The linearity test is carried out to determine whether the data in the study is linear or unidirectionally related or does not have a unidirectional relationship. The results of the linearity test show a linearity sig of $0.000 < 0.05$, while *Deviation from Linearity* $0.552 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the variables have a linear relationship so that they are eligible for regression testing. The results of the linearity test can be seen in table 3.

Anexa

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Model	128.794	1	128.794	4.643	0.032	.008
	Corrected Total	129.794	19	6.831			.008
	Total	142.668	20				

Simple Regression Analysis

Simple regression is a data analysis that tests the hypothesis on the basis of the provisions if sig <0.05, it can show that there is an influence between variable X on Y. In this study, the results of simple regression analysis can be seen in table 4.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.645	1.647		4.643	.000
	X work life balance	.667	.071	.650	9.445	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y kesehatan mental

Based on the results of the calculation of the simple regression equation, it can be seen that the significance value is at 0.000 <0.05, so it can be concluded that there is an influence between the *work life balance* variable on the mental health of millennial generation workers. Furthermore, based on the *Unstandardized Coefficients* column with the contents of the B sub-column which shows the constant a and the amount of the B value. The two coefficients are then summed up with the simple regression equation formula, namely:

$$Y = (\alpha + \beta \cdot X)$$

$$Y = (7.645 + 0.667 X)$$

Based on the data in table 4 of the regression coefficient test, it is known that the t value = 9.445. Regression results are said to be significant if the significance value is <0.05. The decision-making requirements for regression coefficient measurements are as follows.

1. If the probability > 0.05 then Ho is accepted Ha is rejected.
2. If the probability <0.05 then Ho is rejected Ha is accepted.

Hypothesis Test (T Test)

The following are the results of the hypothesis test (t test). The t test basically shows how far the influence of one explanatory or independent variable individually in explaining the dependent variable. [13]. The test was carried out using a *significant level of 0.1* ($\alpha = 10\%$) assisted by the SPSS program. The t test was conducted to test the hypothesis.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.645	1.647		4.643	.000
	X work life balance	.667	.071	.650	9.445	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y kesehatan mental

Table 4.15 shows the results of the significance value for the *work life balance* variable (X) of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05, so *work life balance* has a significant effect. It can be seen that *work life balance* has t_{hitung} greater than t_{tabel} , namely ($9.445 > 1.6574$) with a significance value of 0.000 smaller than 0.05. Thus Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected, meaning that there is a positive and significant influence of the *work life balance* variable (X) on the mental health variable (Y).

Coefficient of Determination Analysis

Based on table 4, the regression coefficient test results can be seen in the Sig or *significance* column, the independent variable and the constant have a significance level below 0.05, so Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected. This means that *work life balance* has a significant effect on mental health. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of *work life balance* on the mental health of millennial generation workers in the Special Region of Yogyakarta.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.650 ^a	.422	.418	3.02599

a. Predictors: (Constant), X work life balance

b. Dependent Variable: Y kesehatan mental

The R Square value or the coefficient of determination used to determine the percentage of influence of the independent variable (predictor) on changes in the dependent variable is 0.650. The R Square value of 0.422 means that the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable (*work life balance*) on changes in the dependent variable (mental health) is 42.2%, while the remaining 57.8% is influenced by other variables not examined.

The results of data analysis show that there is a significant effect of *work life balance* on the mental health of millennial generation workers. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Nafriana (2021) which shows that employees who can manage their time in a balanced manner by being able to divide their personal time with work time without having to harm their work can have a positive impact on the quality of employee mental health. So, it can be said that the better or the higher the application of the balance between work life and employees' personal lives, it can maintain, maintain and improve employees' mental health, so that employees' mental health is not easily disrupted. Then the research conducted by Hendra and Artha (2023) stated that basically work and life balance has a positive impact on employees, companies, and society. For employees, work and life balance can increase job satisfaction, productivity, and physical and mental health. For companies, work-life balance can improve company performance, employee productivity, and the attractiveness of the company as a workplace. For society, work-life balance can improve the well-being of families and society as a whole.

Conclusion

There is an influence of *Work Life Balance* on the Mental Health of Millennial Generation Workers in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. This is indicated by the results of simple linear regression calculations, the t test obtained by the *work life balance* variable has a t count greater than the t table ($9.445 < 1.6574$) with a significance value (0.000) smaller than 0.05.

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination analysis, it can be seen that the *R Square* (R^2) value is 0.422 or 42.2%. This means that 42.2% of the *work life balance* variable can affect the mental health variable, while the remaining 57.8% is explained / influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

Limitations

1. Researchers only use work-life balance variables and their indicators which may not be able to accommodate mental health as a whole.
2. In this study, data was obtained through a questionnaire, which sometimes the answers given by respondents were not really honest from the heart and the researcher could not control the respondents' answers which could not show the real situation.
3. This research largely focuses on Millennial Generation workers in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The narrow geographical scope raises concerns about the generalizability of the findings to each generation across occupations in different regions.

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